

One Genre, Many Formalisms: On Formulaic Language in Pre-Modern Chinese Mathematical Texts

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Introduction

For some technical genres such as mathematics it is often assumed that their language exhibits formulaic characteristics. However, it is notoriously difficult to identify what properties exactly make language “formulaic” (Wray, 2002: 43). In order to nevertheless quantitatively assess the formulaicity of a corpus, Richard Forsyth has proposed a suite of computational tools titled *formulib*, which operates by “compiling a *formulexicon* from a corpus [...] and then us[es] coverage by elements of that *formulexicon* as an index of the degree to which a text [...] is pervaded by formulaic sequences” (Forsyth, 2021: 33). In this study, we apply this suite to pre-modern (ca. 1st century CE to 18th century) Chinese mathematical texts. These texts are particularly interesting because they were written without modern symbolic notation systems, which could suggest more natural, less formulaic patterns of language use. However, previous analysis by Chemla (2006) of a work from the 13th century has shown that pre-modern Chinese mathematical texts can exhibit patterns of artificial language use, which she characterizes by restrictedness, also a key property of Forsyth’s definition of formulaic language (Forsyth 2021: 31). We extend such work analyzing single texts by taking a corpus-based approach that makes it possible to explore how wide-spread formulaic language was in the genre in general.

Corpus and Sampling

The corpus for the study is based on the “Masters Branch” (*zibu* 子部) of the “Complete Library of the Four Treasuries” (*Siku quanshu* 四庫全書, compiled 1772-1782). The “Masters Branch” contains subcategories corresponding to different genres, including philosophy, arts, and different sciences, among them mathematics (Wilkinson, 2022: 1863-1877). Digital versions of the texts were obtained from the “Kanseki Repository 漢籍リポジトリ” (Wittern, 2016).

In a preprocessing step, pre- and postface chapters (*juan* 卷) were removed. Counting rods and numerals, both frequent mathematical texts, were replaced with two distinct place-holder characters, since we are interested in exploring formulaic patterns *with* numbers, e.g. how a multiplication of a number by another number is expressed, but not numbers *as* formulaic patterns on their own.¹

In terms of the contribution of each subcategory and the lengths of the texts within each subcategory, the corpus is highly unbalanced. Hence, random sampling was used to obtain selections of equal text length (based on the 80% quantile of lengths, 3.654 characters) and an equal number of chapters for each subcategory (118, the number in “Math”). The final corpus consists of 11 subcategories with 430.110 tokens (modelling each Chinese character as a token) each, giving a total of 4.731.210 tokens. For validation purposes, the sampling was conducted ten times.

Methodology

The core metric to determine the degree of formulaicity used by Forsyth is *coverage*. Coverage is defined as the number of tokens of the text that occur in the text as a part of at least one of the n -grams in the *formulexicon*, divided by the total number of tokens. The *formulexicon* consist s , with our choice of hyperparameters, of the 80 most frequent n -grams, $3 \leq n \leq 8$, excluding n -grams made up purely of stop words (Forsyth, 2021: 37-40).

Results

Comparing the coverage in mathematics against other genres in the corpus (see Fig. 1), we can confirm that the mathematical language is more formulaic than the other subcategories. However, looking at the mathematical *formulexicon* not only in terms of the frequency of each item, but also its dispersion, measured with document frequency (see Fig. 3), it turns out that the n -grams shared between more than a few texts are limited to a few common operations, such as “multiply it, obtaining n ” (乘之得 n), where n indicates our placeholder for numerals, and expressions for quantities, e.g. “ n parts of n ” (n 分之 n). Furthermore, running the suite using individual works instead of the entire

genre as corpora, we can see that the degree of formulaicity varies drastically between the items (see Fig. 2).

Discussion

Although the result that the language of - at least some of the - mathematical texts was formulaic might not be very surprising, it serves as a confirmation that even before the advent of modern symbolic notation systems, mathematical knowledge was written down using a distinct type of language. A major limitation of the present study is that formulaicity was only examined through the lens of *n*-grams. These *n*-grams might in the future serve as starting points for further research into formulaic language in Chinese mathematics, for example by more closely examining the constructions that are used to express arithmetic operations.

Figure 1: Coverage per genre, with translations from Wilkinson (2022: 1877)

Figure 2: Coverage per title (mathematics only)

Figure 3: Distribution of document frequencies of n-grams in the formulaicon

Footnotes

- Two chapters (not from the mathematical section) were removed due to extensive use of symbols not encoded as Chinese characters.

Bibliography

- Chemla, Karine.** 2006. „Artificial Languages in the Mathematics of Ancient China“. *Journal of Indian philosophy* 34 (1/2): 31–56.
- Forsyth, Richard.** 2021. „Cascading collocations: Collocades as correlates of formulaic language“. In *Formulaic language - Theories and methods*, herausgegeben von Aleksandar Trklja und Łukasz Grabowski. Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Wilkinson, Endymion.** 2022. *Chinese History - A New Manual*. Enlarged sixth edition. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Asia Center.
- Wittern, Christian.** 2016. „Kanseki Repository“. *CIEAS Research Report 2015* Special issue: 1–80.

Wray, Alison. 2002. *Formulaic Language and the Lexicon*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.